

promising entries are given in the table. Highest survival was in IR39558-147-1-3, but because of its longer duration, most panicles did not exsert fully with high salinity and low temperature during Nov.

IR4595-4-1-13-2, IR37257-41-3-2-3, IR40578-13-2-2-3-2-2 with flowering durations of 122, 111, and 93 d, appear most promising. Considering the growth

duration suitable for local situations, IR10198-66-2-1 showed promise.

Among four local varieties tested, Hamilton was most adapted. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Performance of early Prasanna variety

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We grew 3 crops of Prasanna in sequence in 2,000 m² under restricted irrigation at Ramachandrapuram during 1986-87. Sowing was 7 Jul (normal wet season), 22 Aug (midseason), and 20

Dec (normal dry season). Twenty-day-old seedlings were planted at 15- × 15-cm spacing with moderate fertilizer (13-17 kg P-K + 40 kg N/ha). Irrigation at

10-d intervals was applied when there was no rainfall during the 10-d period.

All crops matured in 90 d (see table). Comparing the yields of the Aug and Jul sowings indicated the suitability of Prasanna for midseason planting. Total yield for the year was 8 t/ha, with a 210-d cropping period. □

Performance of Prasanna in a 3-crop year. Hyderabad, India, 1986-87.

Sowing date	Transplanting date	Maturity	Days to maturity	Yield (t/ha)
4 Jul	24 Jul	4 Oct	90	2.4
22 Aug	6 Sep	22 Nov	90	2.6
20 Dec	10 Jan	20 Feb	90	3.0

A high-yielding variety for coastal Andhra Pradesh, India

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MTU7014, a high-yielding, early-maturing, blast-resistant variety, is a derivative of Rasi/IR19667-131-1-2. It consistently yielded higher than BPT1235 in replicated trials during the 1985, 1986, and 1987 dry seasons (see table). In 1987 minikit farmers' field trials at 23 locations in Godavari District, MTU7014 yielded higher than local check BPT1235. □

Agronomic traits and blast resistance of MTU7014 at Maruteru, India, 1986 dry season.

Character	MTU7014	IR64	BPT 1235 (local check)
Plant type	Compact tillers dark green foliage	Compact tillers light green foliage	Low tillers, light green foliage
Growth duration (d)	125	120	120
Plant height (cm)	84	85	86
Panicles (no./m ²)	491	433	528
Spikelets (no./panicle)	99	127	93
Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	97	125	92
Sterility (%)	2.2	1.8	1.1
1000-grain weight (g)	29	28	25
Pigmentation	Green	Green	Purple
Seed dormancy (wk)	4	3	2
Reaction to blast ^a	1	1	8

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9. Tested against race IC 9.

Two new varieties from segregation material of IR36

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IR36 has a growth duration that is too long for an early rice crop in Hunan. We used it as a source of resistance

Yield, growth duration, and pest resistance of 2 new varieties in Hunan, China.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Growth duration (d)	Reaction ^a to			
			BB	B1	BPH	WBPH
IR36 (female)	7.1	125	R	R	R	-
Guong jei 9 (male)	-	109	S	R	S	-
Xiang Zaoxian 3	7.0	106	R	R	R	R
HA79317-4	6.6	102	R	R	R	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

genes for bacterial blight (BB), rice blast (Bl), and brown planthopper (BPH).

Two early rice varieties with medium growth duration—Xiang Zaoxian 3 and

HA793 17-4—have been selected from segregating material of IR36/ Guong jie 9. They have resistance to BB, Bl, BPH, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH),

and high yield (see table). By 1987, they had been planted in 500,000 ha in Hubei, Jiangxi, Guongxi, and Zhejiang Provinces. □

Three rice varieties named in Ghana

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In Ghana, rice is cultivated mostly under rainfed conditions.

C168 from the cross Intan/BPI-76-1 from the Philippines, IR1750-F5-B5 from the cross E425/IR22 from IIRI, and ToX 516-19-Sel from the cross Moroberekan/ Juma I, ToX 7-3-2-3-2, and SE3639 from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) were selected from IRTP trials early in the 1980s.

They consistently have outyielded most other varieties and local checks under rainfed lowland shallow conditions at research sites (Table 1). Even in 1983, with a Jun-Oct growing season rainfall of only 497 mm at Nyankpala and 547 mm at Manga, compared to the 30-yr average 785 mm and 794 mm, yields equaled or were higher than those of the check varieties.

On-farm test yields in 1985 and 1986 also were encouraging (Table 2), and in 1987 the Ghana Rice Varietal Release Committee accepted GR19 (C168), GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5), and GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel) for rainfed cultivation.

GR19 (100 cm tall) matures in about 120 d; GR20 (90 cm), in 105 d; and GR21 (90 cm), in 110 d. All have acceptable cooking and eating qualities and are resistant or moderately resistant to leaf blast and brown spot. □

Table 1. Grain yield and reactions to blast and brown spot of GR19, GR20, and GR21 under rainfed conditions at research sites in Ghana, 1981-85.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)					Reaction ^a to		
	1981 (1 site)	1982 (2 sites)	1983 ^a (2 sites)	1984 (3 sites)	1985 (9 sites)	Mean ^b	Blast	Brown spot
GR19 (C168)	3.8	2.1	1.2	2.6	2.0	2.3 (46%)	2	3
GR20 (IR1750-F5-B5)	4.4	2.4	1.6	1.7	2.1	2.4 (53%)	3	2
GR21 (ToX 516-19-Sel)	4.4	2.4	1.0	2.8	2.5	2.6 (65%)	3	3
Check variety Tamale 1	2.4	1.4	1.0	1.4	1.8	1.6	7	5

^aRainfall deficit was 247-288 mm at trial sites. ^bPercentages show yield increase over check variety. ^cBy the Standard evaluation systems for rice scale.

Table 2. On-farm trial grain yield of GR19, GR20, and GR21 in Ghana, 1985 and 1986.

Site	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	GR19	GR21	GR20	Local check
	1985			
Nayoko	2.6	2.8	2.9	1.7
Zawse	2.2	2.8	2.8	1.6
Zabgo	0.9	1.7	2.3	2.2
Gore	0.4	0.6	1.3	0.5
Vane	3.4	4.9	2.7	2.8
Mean	1.9	2.6	2.4	1.8
	1986			
Tarkpaa 1	2.2	2.4		1.3
Tarkpaa 2	2.9	1.8		2.1
Tarkpaa 3	1.7	1.2		0.8
Cheshegu	2.4	2.2		1.4
Zuarungu	3.7	^a		2.9
Soe 1	0.9	0.8		0.7
Soe 2	5.2	5.2		5.6
Bladjei	1.5	1.6		1.1
Katiejeli	0.9	0.6		1.3
Tarkpaa 4	3.0	3.1		3.0
Kete Krachi	2.9	3.5		3.8
Kpassa/Nkwanta	^a	3.3		1.4
Central Volta	2.6	2.9		1.0
Gbefi	3.3	3.9		1.2
Vane	^a	2.3		2.0
Mean	2.6	2.5		2.0

^aNot included.

Red Triveni, a promising short-duration variety for India

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Of three short-duration, semidwarf, high-yielding rice varieties released in Kerala, Triveni is the most popular among Kerala farmers. Farmers who have a strong preference for red grain have been asking for a red-grained version, adaptable to all growing seasons.

About 5 yr after Triveni's release, a few isolated red-grained plants were found. Red-grained plants reoccurred, despite strict roguing.

White-grained PTB15, one of the parents in the evolution of Triveni, has purple tipping. Possibly, segregation for